

TELEVISION EFFICIENCY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TRAINING

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Annotation: *in the modern world, where globalization is taking place, the level of knowledge of foreign languages, in particular English, is becoming more important in every area. Today, the main task of teaching a foreign language is to freely express the thought in the studied international language, both oral and written, and to train literate youth with a developed culture of speech and communication. This article will talk about the role of televedinie in the effective and rapid assimilation of languages, as well as shows on the promotion of foreign languages in the national media space*

Keywords: *Foreign Language Teaching, television, modern information technology, media space capabilities, efficiency*

Nowadays, the Internet has evolved and has become the main source of information dissemination. Still, the media, especially television, are still leading in terms of bringing information to the general public and the scale of impact. Billions of people on earth watch TV every day to stay up to date with the latest

events, enjoy the shows and elephants they like, and spend their time in general in a meaningful way. This is why television appears as a powerful tool that affects public opinion, as well as its spirituality and mental potential. Based on the requirements of today's time, it can be said that even when teaching foreign languages, TV shows

dedicated to the promotion of foreign languages broadcast on television have little effect.

It should be noted that it was for this purpose that the broadcast TV shows were first prepared by employees of a foreign television company. We can give a number of examples of such telemedicine products created under the authorship of journalists operating in such large countries of the world as the USA, Russia, Italy, Spain, France, Germany.

In particular, only a few projects such as "polyglot", "Hablamos en español", which were broadcast on the Russian TV channel "Kultura", have managed to find proof of their effectiveness in practice.¹ The reason for the reforms carried out throughout our country and in the direction in recent years has also increased significantly in the Uzbek media space, in particular on TV channels, the number of broadcasts dedicated to the promotion of foreign languages.

Various popular science and Marathi shows, foreign artistic and multiplicative films, News are regularly shown on television in English. Experts believe that watching the shows that will be shown in the language being studied is equally useful both for a skilled translator and for those who are just learning the language.² Today, in order to master a foreign language

well, the use of educational materials is lacking in itself. For this, it is necessary to use more of a live communication tool that allows you to further increase vocabulary, pronounce correctly, improve oral speech and broaden your horizons. Taking into account these aspects, a number of projects aimed at teaching a foreign language through the National Broadcasting Company of Uzbekistan are regularly implemented.

This process, especially in May 2021, President Sh. It would not be a mistake to say that Mirziyoyev was taken to another higher level on the basis of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to bring the activities of popularization of foreign languages \ u200b \ u200b to a qualitatively new level". In the past period, a priority task reflected in the decision was created - the agency for the popularization of the study of foreign languages.

Since December 2021, one of the important tasks assigned to the organization was the launch of the TV channel "foreign languages" (Foreign languages) in the MTRK system of Uzbekistan.⁴ This TV channel aims to popularize foreign languages among the population, especially among the younger generation, and takes on tasks such as giving popular science,

documentary, feature films, TV shows, tutorials to help students master international languages, and promoting the development of language skills.

Today, the creators of the TV channel have prepared broadcasts in 6 languages (English, Russian, French, German, Korean and Turkish) in different genres and directions and will be presented to the audience. During the week, from Monday to Saturday, live broadcasts with the participation of local and foreign linguists are also regularly held. The TV channel also covers programs on international language lessons, literature analysis, culture of nations and specific traditions. The audience of the shows aimed at Language Teaching is not limited, special projects have been created even for children. At first, in part, the Uzbek language was also used in television projects, and to date, creative products are being prepared on the TV channel "foreign languages" (Foreign languages) in the specified language almost one hundred percent.

In addition, at the moment there are also foreign-language information and entertainment programs on the TV channels "around the world", "youth" and "Kidajon". In particular, through the TV channel "Kidajon" a number of shows are broadcast, which aim to

form the language skills of young viewers.

Examples of this are programs such as "Abc kids", "Funny dictionary", "Fairy tales", where knowledge of the English language is given. In order to ensure the effectiveness and interest of the shows, the creators use the achievements of various interactive games and the latest modern information technologies in the preparation of products.

Fans of the TV channel "Kidajon", who are not indifferent to the study of foreign languages, also enjoy such TV shows as "English lessons", "Happy alphabet". It must be said that more than 10 programs dedicated to the promotion of foreign languages have been broadcast through the TV channel to this day.

Today, in order to master a foreign language well, the use of educational materials itself is scarce. For this, it is necessary to use more of a live communication tool that allows you to further increase vocabulary, pronounce correctly, improve oral speech and broaden your horizons.⁵ Taking into account the fact that television is of great importance in the life of society, we can say that the use of its help in teaching foreign languages is one of the rational measures at the moment.

The national television and radio company of Uzbekistan, which

pays attention to these aspects, is definitely implementing a number of projects aimed at teaching its audience a foreign language. Nevertheless, the level of quality of programs, the lack of specialists who perfectly master foreign languages, audience coverage are some of the pressing issues that still need to be addressed in the direction. In the future, the range of broadcasts on television will be further expanded, which will include foreign languages of schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges

it would be advisable if, using the lessons of their teachers, who have great professional experience and mature potential in teaching, even more interesting shows were prepared in cooperation with international organizations and did not leave indifferent the youth of today, and they were widely promoted through the Internet and social networks. These programs, in turn, as an additional lesson, carry out a kind of methodological assistance both for young people studying the language in all educational institutions of our country and for specialists teaching the language. In addition, it opens the door to great opportunities even for young people from remote regions of our country.

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